

Machine Learning Approaches for Predicting and Preventing Adverse Cardiovascular Events

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Abstract- Over the last 10 years, a significant surge in cardiovascular diseases has been observed around the world. Considering the cruciality of the disease leads to rapid action toward the development of accurate cardiovascular disease risk prediction. However, currently, existing methods often fail to predict cardiovascular disease risk to diagnose patients that could have benefited via preventive treatment, while in other cases patients go through dispensable interceding. Machine learning techniques offer for cardiovascular disease prediction not only detect disease risk with maximum accuracy and precision but also exploit complex interactions for better disease prognosis. Effective and timely prediction of cardiovascular disease using patients' health records not only assists in rapid diagnosis but also reduces mortality rate. In this article, we present a detailed comparative analysis of existing machine-learning techniques for cardiovascular disease prediction and prevention. Our research shows extensive analysis of around 35 papers related to machine learning-based cardiovascular disease prediction. This study will not only summarize the existing up-to-date approaches but also assist doctors in predicting heart disease risks before time, providing ample time for precautionary actions.

Keywords- Artificial intelligence, machine learning, Cardiovascular Diseases, Heart Disease Risk Prediction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular disease is primarily caused by abnormality in heart functioning. Heart disease risk frequency increases with the age and is the most in old age people, however, these days an increase surge in heart disease problem is observed in people of all ages, including infants, new born, kids, young generation and elderly. All of them are equally getting affected from heart problems and chronic heart stroke risks. There are a number of such cardiovascular diseases where some of them are genetically transferred problems while others include Heart vessel arrest, Down syndrome, Coronary artery blockage (CAB), Value heart disease, myocardial infarctions and many others [1].

All around the world cardiovascular diseases (CVD) are one of the major causes of death. An estimated 18 million deaths were recorded in 2022 from cardiovascular disease amongst which 8 million deaths are utterly caused by coronary heart disease while the other 7 million were due to a heart attack. Primary factors for determining cardiovascular disease risk include age, smoking, cholesterol, diabetes, and hypertension [2]. There is a strong association of all these risk factors with increased CVD risk.

The primary approaches and tools devised for CVD prediction included risk assessment protocol by the American Heart Association (American College of Cardiology (ACC/AHA),

QRISK (QRESEARCH cardiovascular risk algorithm) score that is primarily for coronary disease risk prediction, Framingham Risk Score that is dependent on factors including blood pressure age, high-density lipoprotein (HDL), smoking, gender, and total cholesterol [3]. It predicts coronary artery disease (CAD) events when applied to HIV patients during therapy. Despite the presence of all these tools there remain a large number of patients at CVD risk and fail to get recognized by these approaches, while on the contrary some of the individuals receive excessive unnecessary risk prevention treatment.

Around 50 % of heart stroke and myocardial infarctions patients were the ones who were not even predicted at the risk of cardiovascular disease [4]. All of the cardiovascular disease risk prediction models work on the assumption that every risk factor is directly related to CVD outcome linearly. Therefore, these models at times disregard the variable relationship complexity that includes non-linear interactivity with the risk factor. There exist techniques that utilize these risk implications and output a precise relationship between the risk factors and their results.

One such domain where a surge in CVD prediction and prevention techniques is seen is Machine learning. Machine learning models learn nonlinearities and complex relationships amongst the risk variables and utilize a separate loss function and optimizers for reducing the error between the predicted and the actual result. It exports “big data” and trains a large number of structured as well as unstructured data for developing the complex relationship amongst variables and non-linearity [5]. Furthermore, it also identifies underlying variables that were left unrecognized or derived from main factors, thus enhancing the overall prediction score.

This study aims at reviewing existing machine learning techniques that are available in the literature for cardiovascular disease risk prediction and prevention.

II. MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES FOR CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE RISK PREDICTION & PREVENTION

For the prediction of cardiovascular disease, many different machine learning-based techniques have been proposed by researchers. Reference [6] focused on the J48 tree technique and compared the outcome with the Random forest algorithm and Logistic tree model. J48 predicted results with an accuracy of 59%. Reference [7] implemented five different algorithms while the highest accuracy is obtained from the K Nearest Neighbour technique. While [8] used Naive Bayes Classifier, Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, Logistic Regression, and Support Vector Machine for the prediction of Cardiovascular risk where the SVM model outperformed the other techniques with a precision of 91%.

Reference [9] devised a model based on multiple machine learning techniques and used a dataset from UCI having 16 attributes and predicted better accuracy than previous techniques with a precision of around 91% via utilizing a hard ensemble voting technique. Similarly [10] utilized a backward elimination technique that is a machine learning method for training and experimenting heart disease dataset. They used five different techniques for training data, amongst which logistic regression techniques exhibited the best cardiovascular disease prediction accuracy of around 83%. Contrary to this [11] proposed an app-based method for streamlining the entire procedure where data is processed and monitored through MLib spark and spark-based streaming is then utilized for processing the pipeline. This method achieved an accuracy of around 79%, where the percentage of specificity and sensitivity is about 80% and 83% simultaneously. It also collated the processing time taken in the traditional method and the proposed spark technique and undoubtedly a remarkable refinement is observed by the spark technique.

Reference [12] proposed a hybrid machine learning based algorithm for predicting cardiovascular disease, this technique is based of hybrid random forest with linear model (HRFLM) which basically originated from the linear model and random forest. It achieved an overall accuracy of around 85%. A genetic algorithm based disease risk prediction technique is proposed by [13], where the fitness function is determined from the algorithm variables including crossover, tournament selection and mutation. The results determined from this method were around 77% accurate. This technique also opened up a new avenue for using deep neural networks for CVD risk prediction.

Reference [14] proposed a method for cardiovascular disease risk forecast for prevention in future based on the Multi Linear regression Model based on its accurate prognostic automated performance. In this study, the used about 400 entities having 15 different variables where 75% of the data is exploited for training while the remaining 25% is kept for testing purposes. This method performed better than the previously discussed technique and gave reliable results.

A data mining technique based on the weka tool and 10 cross-validation is proposed for risk assessment [15].

They utilized KNN, J48, Native Bayes, Multilayer perceptron, SVM, and Bayes Net. Amongst these techniques, the best performance is obtained by the Bayes Net model compared to Kstar and MLP. Despite giving better results a considerable lag in performance is still observed in this technique. Further enhancements are done for accurate risk prognosis. Another technique proposed by [16] utilized three machine learning algorithms for patients' illness-based disease forecasting based on the input data. Algorithms used in this research include Artificial Neural network, random forest, and naïve Bayes and it predicted the results based on the performance accuracy comparison of the techniques. Random forest yielded better results compared to the ANN and Naïve Bayes algorithms.

An amalgamation of categorization-based techniques including Naïve Bayes, artificial neural network, SVM, and K nearest neighbour strategy is proposed by [17]. Contrary to traditional approaches, Logistic Regression (LR) techniques yielded best performance. A predictive model is constructed based on the data mining techniques for cardiovascular disease by [18]. They employed an illness diagnostic approach termed WEKA in medical units and health centers for providing better assessment quality. In this study, the authors used distinct ML techniques including KNN, Decision Trees, SVM, Cluster Analysis, and ANN. Amongst all of the techniques used SVM predicted with the highest accuracy compared to the rest of the data mining approaches.

A nonlinear categorization-based approach is proposed by [19] for predicting cardiovascular disease. They study predicted the cardiovascular disease risk via 3 different ML techniques including Hadoop Distributed File System, SVM and MapReduce. This approach checks the chances of heart disease based on the input data. HDFS is based on decentralized distributed storage mechanism which utilized Support Vector machine for massive data execution in parallel on different nodes. Major reason behind using SVM instead of sequential method is its time efficiency and faster calculation.

Reference [20] devised a method for accurate parameter-based decision. They employed data technology and machine learning for forecasting heart stroke risk. They predicted around 88% accuracy during the training phase and 87% in the test phase. In 2016, [21] presented an approach using artificial neural networks (ANN) for predicting heart disease risk. The proposed prediction technique interprets data from distinct patient variables, factors including heart rate, age, cholesterol levels, blood pressure and others, in a thorough diagnostic fashion. The increasing rate of cardiovascular disease shows the inevitable need for the development of an accurate and fast methods. The accuracy of this methods is demonstrated through its implementation in Pythonn.

In 2018, [22] proposed a technique for predicting heart disease by utilizing individual level clinical metadata of patients. The development of this method is based on fifteen distinct risk variables. Firstly, the comprehensive analysis of the dataset, data ingestion is done, then the integration and cleaning of data were performed.

Reference [23] introduced an approach that investigated the exploitation of data mining and ML techniques for assessment of heart disease risk. The study aims to achieve two objectives. Firstly, it disregarded the previous patient records and the method focused on cardiac illnesses forecasting. Secondly for handling the bulk amount of documentation available, the technique employs scalar processing. The methods is executed via using the WEKA tool, and for testing purposes, WEKA categorization software is used.

III. CHALLENGES IN CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE RISK ASSESSMENT

Despite the significance of Machine learning based Machine learning-based cardiovascular disease (CVD) risk prediction and prevention. The methods suggested in the studies faces some major challenges. The first and foremost issue faced during ML based CVD prediction is quality of data and its availability. In majority of the time obtaining a standard better quality, disparate data with distinct variables is it self a major challenge compared to training a model [24].

One of the primary reasons is data limitation, incompleteness and inconsistency in health care domain. And even after fetching the data other issue come up including missing data, discrepancy in collected data and partial values. The second major challenge is the cardiac disease datasets are most of the times imbalanced, the positively diagnosed patients data is too less in contrast to negatively diagnosed patients which are the ones predicted as not having cardiovascular disease. Without balancing such data and training the model directly on this raw data impacts the performance of the model and it results in under-training. For rectifying this issue there are some augmentation techniques proposed including oversampling or under-sampling, SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique) and other techniques as well [25].

Data dimensionality and proper selection of feature is also a big challenge. Since there are many feature variables involved in the risk assessment of heart disease including biomarker data, previous medical data of the patient, individual lifestyle, and patient demographics. In these cases, the analysis of right feature along with maintain data dimensionality if a crucial task. For addressing this challenge appropriate feature selection technique is required for extracting proper data along with mitigating the over-fitting issue and enhancing the interpretability of the model.

The major reason behind ensuring the model interpretability is the importance of accurate and precise results in health care as the more precise the algorithm is the better it will develop the interest of doctors and patients and gain their trust as well [26].

Different machine learning techniques are still interpreted as “black box” algorithms for example SVMs where its difficult to make the process understand to someone outside the domain. In such scenarios developing self-explainable approaches is inevitable for better risk assessment and evaluation by clinicians. Cardiovascular disease risk aspects and its significance differs and ranges from distinct regions, countries diverse population and beliefs.

Devising a generalized approach that can target all different ethnicities is itself a bigger issue that demands an in depth analysis of data representative’s, proper risk factor utilization feature engineering, and technique validation in different groups. Machine learning techniques can inadvertently inherit biases present in the evaluation data, leading to over-fitted, or under-fitted model leading biased results for every [27]. This challenge is extremely critical and can be resolved by highlighting and addressing the major bias variables in data including gender, age, race and socioeconomic factors for ensure bias less and fair prediction in CVD risk prediction and prevention systems.

IV. DISCUSSION & PRINCIPLE FINDINGS

The world is in dire need of better models for predicting the risk of events of cardiovascular because there is a significant increase in the average number of patients who contain cardiovascular diseases [28]. There are so many models that are frequently in use all over the world. Let’s take the example of the use of a risk prediction statistical model which is consistently available for cardiovascular events, this model caters to the needs of so many problems but still, it is not fully reliable because the ability to predict the risk of individual level is lacking in this statistically based risk prediction model.

There we use machine learning, which is reliable to deal with at the individual level, machine learning is used to predict and provide accurate results for the prediction of risk at the individual level [29]. Furthermore, Machine learning models are specially made to handle complex data. The theoretical evidence supports the evidence that Machine learning models are more reliable than if we compare them with statistical based models for predicting cardiovascular events. Machine learning models provide results of cardiovascular events of the individual risk level. On the other hand, the statistical-based model can be effective if it is used at the population level than the individual level [30]. Studies suggest that algorithms of machine learning, specifically deep neural networks, are more proficient and reliable than other machine learning algorithms in outcomes particularly related to cardiovascular events.

A large amount of data poses complexity and difficulties for computer science scientists to deal with the data which is generated from records, studies, and other sources of electronic health, they face several challenges in interpreting the data, moreover, analysing it, and if data is put into the context of clinics [31]. It is expected that the health industry of the US will generate data of trillion megabytes, with the expected growth of approximately 35 Machine learning models play a significant role in structural diseases of the heart and its interventions will be paramount. The ongoing studies are more towards the work on specific disease which are focused on patient clustering and reclassification of it and checking the results getting from using similarity analysis of patients. In the detailed view, patients' similarity analysis is done by presenting patients as nodes and after that, those nodes are interlinked with the use of edges that gives the outcome of showing the patient's similarities. From the patient similarity analysis, it is revealed that there is a heterogeneous relationship between the patient, and it gives us a graphical representation and shows the networked data in a graphical format. Algorithms Of machine learning outperform others, but still, further studies are required to test the capability and testing its effectiveness in the scenario of real-world complex data. By conducting the test researchers can check the potential and benefits of using this deep network algorithm of machine learning.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study we have investigated the machine learning models proposed in the literature for the prediction and risk assessment of cardiovascular disease. In the coming fifty years, the number of heart diseases cases and death toll due to CVD will continue to increase. Therefore, the primary objective is to apply machine learning methods instead of following traditional cardiovascular disease prediction methods that yield correct results for linear data but performance suddenly drop down in complex representation non linear dataset. This article focuses on reviewing existing machine learning techniques for examining and predicting heart disease abnormalities at an early stage. Machine learning models integrates machine intelligence technologies and fetch insights from input data and on its basis reduces training error and leads precise findings along with increasing performance accuracy. Majority of the models have used SVM, LR, RF, KNN, K-means, ANN and J48 as training model and yielded accuracies ranging from 67% up to 94%. Some of the techniques have also utilized "big data" for initial data exploration, cleaning and insights and pre-processed data is then fed into HDFS or Spark models for data parallel processing at different nodes, This article is beneficial for early computer science researchers in cardiac disease for providing existing literature insights, doctor, diagnosis and prognostic investigators for perceiving patterns for cardiovascular disease risk assessment and prevention.

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